

GridSys- A state of the art grid framework

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Abstract—Today many applications are developed using distributed technologies such as cluster, cloud and grid computing. These applications demand more resources for computation and storage. They demand flexible scaling and improved performance. Application now days can make use of multiple nodes (machines) to get the tasks completed. In this paper we discuss the implementation details of a grid computing framework known as GridSys. This framework provides a fast and easy way to program a grid. It can easily help the application break the problem to compute intensive tasks. The framework distributes these tasks to different nodes of the grid efficiently and easily aggregate the results of these tasks provide fault tolerance and reliability.

Keywords- Grid Computing, Framework, Parallel Processing

I. INTRODUCTION

Grid Computing [1] has been one of most popular distributed computing technologies. It helps to harness the power of all computers which are connected to a network. Most popular applications that can use grid computing technology include genetic algorithms; image processing [2], simulation and modeling [3] etc. These applications are very resource intensive (memory and compute intensive) and therefore must use distributed technologies to improve the computational speed.

There are many popular grid computing frameworks available today. Alchemi [4] is a grid computing initiative from the University of Melbourne. It is implemented using .NET technology. The framework aims at using desktops running windows operating system to form a grid. The framework also supports xml based job scheduling where the jobs description is provided in an xml. The limitation of Alchemi is that it cannot handle large number of nodes, does not support customizing of schedulers and scheduling algorithms. It cannot handle multiple application and re-distribution of tasks and does not support automatic and manual exclusion of grid nodes. It does not support initialization and un-initialization tasks and does not have a failsafe mechanism.

Globus [5] is an enterprise grid framework build in Java. It uses web services as part of implementation. It has services related to resource allocation, storage, replication, scheduling, data access and integration. It also has support for authentication and authorization. Legion [6] aimed at connecting millions of computer through a high speed link and holds them together so that users can get an illusion of single virtual supercomputer.

Legion tries to abstract hardware components such as processors, software such as scheduling and data migration components. Some of its important goals are to provide site autonomy, extensibility, scalability, seamless computational environment etc. It also supports programming in multiple languages and supports different operating systems on the computer which form the part of the Grid. The configuration and customization of Globus and Legion is complex in nature and time consuming. The users need to have in depth knowledge of the toolkit and does not support special task types like initialization and un-initialization.

In this paper we explain in detail the implementation of a grid computing framework known as GridSys, which can utilize the capabilities of any type of machines (nodes) ranging from low end desktops to high end servers. We explain the technical specifications and the top level architecture; we give an overview of each and every component which forms the part of GridSys. We explain how important aspects such as fault tolerance, scalability, reliability are incorporated within the framework. Some use cases are also explained along with quantitative results to justify the improvements seen in the applications using the GridSys.

II. IMPLEMENTATION SPECIFICATIONS

GridSys has a layered architecture. The Client Layer consists of a client application which wants to use the capabilities of the grid framework to solve a computationally intensive problem. The client application uses the GridSys library's application programming interface (API) to access the framework's capabilities. The library provides APIs that help the client application split the complex task into various smaller tasks that can be executed in parallel. A Client Broker connects the GridSys framework layer with the application layer and controls the interaction between them. The GridSys framework layer contains various components that help to distribute and manage the tasks across the available compute nodes. The layer contains dynamic queues, a Controller, a File Transfer Service, a Scheduler, a Registrar and Processors which run on multiple compute nodes. Each of the components will be explained in detail. Figure 1 depicts the interaction between the components in the GridSys framework.

Figure 1. Component interaction in GridSys

A. Client Application

A client application is a program which wants to use the capabilities of GridSys to solve a complex problem. The problem should be decomposable to tasks which can be executed independently on any node. Examples of such application include image processing, simulation; data analysis, software builds etc. The client application will use the GridSys library to achieve this goal.

B. GridSys Library

The library is a set of standard APIs to be used by the client application or a program to access the capabilities of the framework. The GridSys library provides functionalities such as connecting to the grid, uploading large files, defining a user task that can be executed independently. It also supports defining initialization tasks that are to be executed before the actual tasks are executed, mechanism for starting and stopping the task execution on the grid, notifications for completion or failure of tasks. The library also supports defining the un-initialization tasks. These tasks can perform any action related

to clean up after the execution of actual task. All the tasks and action are grouped under the SGApplication (GridSys application) instance which has a unique id known as the Application Id. The user defined tasks can be broadly of three types, InitJob (initialization task), NormalJob (user defined application specific tasks) and UninitJob (cleanup or un-initialization Task).

C. Client Broker and Queues.

The Client Broker acts as an abstraction between the client application and the grid framework components. It hides the framework internal implementation details from the client application. It is responsible for creating, managing and deletion of application specific queues. The queue names are unique to each application and are generated with the help of application id. These queues are created when the client application tries to connect to the grid. The broker creates two queues per application; the input queue and the output queue. The broker also listens to the queue known as the application queue. The input queue is used by the broker to push the different application tasks to the grid framework's controller in the form of messages. The broker collects the results from the output queue and forwards it to the client application using

notifications. The Client Broker is also responsible to collect the files from the client application and upload to the File Transfer Service for use by the framework components. The application specific input queue and output queue are deleted by the broker when all the results are obtained and forwarded to the application.

D. File Transfer Service.

The File Transfer Service (FTS) holds the files supplied by the client application. It supports upload and download of files. The client application uploads single or multiple files to the FTS through the client broker. The files are stored in the form of key value pairs where the application id is the key and the value is the set of files to upload or download. The FTS supports upload and download of physical files and in memory data structures like class instances, collections such as vector and dictionaries and custom types.

E. The Registrar

The Registrar is a component responsible for keeping track of the processors which are part of GridSys. Whenever a new processor is added, an entry corresponding to the node and the processor is updated in the registrar. Each processor registers itself with a unique id and advertises its capabilities. The registrar maintains a heartbeat mechanism between the registered processors. A processor may be unregistered automatically by the registrar when the processor is not reachable by a heart beat mechanism. The processor may also be manually unregistered not to be part of GridSys. In both of these scenarios, the entry corresponding to processor is removed by the registrar. It also supports retrieving the list processor for assigning tasks by the controller.

F. Controller .

The controller is responsible for distributing the tasks of the client application to the processors. It also takes care of load balancing of the nodes/processors. The controller listens to a queue from which the broker sends the information about the application. It also creates an instance of a scheduler corresponding to an application. If multiple applications are obtained then multiple instance of the schedulers are created, however the number of processors are equally divided and provided to the schedulers. The controller is also capable of starting or stopping the scheduler depending on the needs of the client application.

G. Scheduler

The scheduler is responsible for scheduling the tasks to processors. It receives the tasks from application specific input queue which the controller listen to. The scheduling logic is customizable. Whenever the tasks are completed by the processors, the results are sent to the broker through the output queue. The scheduler also implements different failure management mechanisms. For example if a task execution

from any of the processor fails, it reschedules the task to a processor in some other node. The scheduler runs as a separate logical process in the controller. This is because if the scheduler terminates due to some faults, the failure can be isolated and restarted without affecting other schedulers running in the controller. The application specific queues provide a reliable persistence mechanism. This facilitates the scheduler to restart from the point where the scheduler terminated.

H. Processors or Worker Services.

The processors execute the tasks scheduled by the scheduler. The processors run in multiple nodes. A node can have more than one processor depending on the resources present in the node like memory, available CPU etc. Processors notify the scheduler on successful or failed task execution and pass the result back to the scheduler. The processor is also a customizable component. The GridSys framework provides public interfaces for extension of the processors. These customizations can be easily deployed to multiple nodes. The processor can be stopped automatically when the task execution fail in the processor consecutively. The processor can be manually stopped by the user when he would not want his machine resources be used by the framework.

I. The Workflow (Putting it All together)

The client application negotiates a connection to GridSys from the broker using the GridSys library. The broker grants the connection with a unique application id. The client application pushes the files and other dependencies to the broker. These files and dependencies are uploaded to the File Transfer Service by the broker using application id as key. The client application then defines a set of independent tasks for execution by extending the public interfaces provided by the GridSys library. The client application prepares an initialization task, a set of normal execution tasks, and a un-initialization task. It also specifies the mode of initialization and un-initialization (either per-processor or per-node). In the per-processor mode, all the processors execute the initialization task before executing the normal tasks and execute a un-initialization on completion. In the per-node mode, the initialization and un-initialization tasks runs only once per node.

The client application subscribes to the GridSys framework events provided by the library for success or failure notifications of the task execution. It then instructs the framework to start processing the tasks as per the instruction. The broker creates dynamic input queue and the output queue with the help of application id. The Broker then extracts the information of client application and creates a message. The message would contain the mode of initialization/un-initialization, the type of the application, input queue name and the output queue name. The Broker pushes this message to the application queue. This is also called as a start message.

The controller listening to application queue receives the message and gets the list of available processors from the registrar, the input queue name, the output queue name, application Id and the application type. It creates an instance with a unique id and supplies all the parameters to it and instructs the scheduler to listen to a specific input queue. The Broker starts pushing the tasks to the input queue with the first task as initialization task. The scheduler picks the first task i.e. the initialization task. It analyses whether the initialization task is per processor or per machine and schedule this tasks to the nodes accordingly. The scheduler does not schedule normal tasks until the processors in the nodes are initialized. In the processor initialization task is executed and then the dependencies that were uploaded for use by FTS are downloaded by the processors on the nodes by specifying the application id.

The processors notify the scheduler that they are ready to execute normal tasks. The scheduler schedules the normal tasks to them. The processors execute the task and notify the scheduler with result. If the execution is successful the results are pushed to the output queue which the broker listens to. If the task execution has failed, it is rescheduled to some other processor. If consecutive failures are noticed on particular nodes, the scheduler excludes these nodes and continues rescheduling to other nodes. If the failure still continues the failed results of each execution are pushed to the output queue. The broker collects all the messages regardless of failure or success and notifies the results to the client application. When all the tasks are completed or client application plans to stop processing, the client application initiates a connection closure from the Broker. Broker sends an end message to the application queue. On receiving the end message, the scheduler stops listening to the input queue and schedules un-initialization tasks. After successful execution of un-initialization tasks (cleanup tasks) in processor, it notifies the controller to reclaim all the processors. The scheduler sends the acknowledgement token of receipt of end message and ends its life time. The Broker receives the acknowledgement token and deletes the input queue and the output queue specific to the application. The broker then notifies the client application of successful termination of the connection. The client application clears all resources used.

III. EXPERIMENT AND RESULTS

A client application to improve the build speed was developed using GridSys. The application used GridSys with 4 nodes of quad core machines with 4GB RAM with two processors added from each node. The improvement brought about by GridSys is represented in Table 1.

No of software components	Time taken (minutes)		% improvement in build time
	Normal Build	Build with GridSys	
300	240	30	87.5
420	300	47	84.3
864	600	54	91
1110	650	60	91
1200	800	90	89
1500	825	90	89

Table 1. Build time comparison study

IV. CONCLUSION

The GridSys framework harnesses parallel processing capabilities of multiple nodes. It provides simple APIs to configure parallel tasks and extension points to customize the tasks, schedulers and workers/processors. It provides notifications for task scheduling in terms of failure or success. It provides the flexibility to integrate new scheduling algorithms or reuse existing ones. It also provides out of the box features such as running initialization and clean-up tasks and load balancing capabilities. When multiple client applications try to use the grid, the workers are redistributed across multiple schedulers. It has task resuming capabilities even after failure due to the reliability built into it using message queues for persistence. It has a mechanism to support both manual and automatic exclusion of nodes from the grid. A monitoring framework is being implemented to track resources in the nodes.

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